

LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS FOR COMBATING CORRUPTION IN SERBIA

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Abstract

Corruption is a phenomenon known from the earliest days of human civilization that has persisted to this day and represents a huge danger to the survival of the community. In the report, the basic concepts and characteristics of corruption, the international and national legislative framework and institutional mechanisms for its suppression in the Republic of Serbia are briefly presented. The place, role and tasks of the newly established specialized authorities of the police, prosecutor's office and the judiciary for the fight against corruption were especially pointed out. Furthermore, an overview of the most important activities and achieved results in combating corruption in Serbia in the last few years is provided. In the final part, some solutions *de lege ferenda* are proposed to improve the legislative framework and improve the work of specialized bodies for combating corruption. Special attention was paid to Serbia's application for admission to the EU and, in connection with that, the need for harmonization of regulations, further development of good practice and construction of functional mechanisms.

Keywords: corruption, corrupt crimes, suppression of corruption, Republic of Serbia, EU.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of the third millennium, corruption is an indisputable global problem that seriously erodes the foundations of modern society, represents a threat to democracy and the modern rule of law. This is a phenomenon known since the earliest days of human civilization that has survived many changes and has remained until today. In modern society of technical and technological development, corruption has taken on new and more dangerous forms, especially in transition and developing countries. Unfortunately, in many underdeveloped areas, corruption has acquired the right of citizenship and has become a phenomenon that is taken for granted, to which citizens are accustomed and rarely react.

Corruption of members of the public service is particularly present in developing countries, countries in transition and underdeveloped areas. This entails the devastation of public services, state administration bodies and local self-government, which increases citizens' mistrust in these institutions and their officials.

After the fall of the Berlin Wall, the problem of corruption was encountered by many ex-socialist countries that did not have a good normative basis and did not have

built-in mechanisms to fight corruption. Many of these countries, such as Poland, Hungary, the Czech Republic, Slovakia and others, have relatively successfully completed the process of economic and social transition, and have built sustainable mechanisms to fight crime and corruption, as one of the most serious forms of crime. Most Eastern European countries joined the EU after the changes and accepted the standards and mechanisms for fighting corruption and other forms of crime.

The Republic of Serbia and other successor states of the former SFRY also faced economic and other problems after the breakup of the common state, as well as a high rate of crime and especially corruption. Some of them, such as Slovenia and Croatia, had great support from Western countries and successfully completed the economic and social transition, so they were admitted to equal membership of the EU. Other countries from the former SFRY are today still in the process of transition and social reforms, and have applied for EU membership.

Regarding accession to EU membership, Serbia started negotiations even earlier and opened numerous negotiation chapters with the aim of harmonizing legal norms with EU regulations, accepting good practices and prevailing solutions of the EU. Chapters No. 23 and No. 24 are particularly important, which refer to the judiciary and fundamental rights, justice, freedom and security, with which Serbia and other candidate countries need to be aligned. In this part, the fight against corruption, which seriously disrupts the socio-economic system, life in the community and cancels the results achieved in the process of transition and social changes, has a significant place. Suppression of corruption and all its manifestations is also important for strengthening the reputation of the state and its bodies, building citizens' trust in the system and affirming the principle of the rule of law.

2. METHODS

The paper explores the legislative aspects of corruption and accordingly uses methods of legal sciences such as dogmatic, normative and comparative law methods. Using the same methods, institutional mechanisms used in the fight against corruption are abstracted from legal regulations and their analysis is performed. In addition, content analysis of literature and previous research on corruption is used.

3. ABOUT CORRUPTION IN GENERAL

In a historical sense, corruption is a phenomenon known from the earliest days of human civilization in the form of favours, gifts and dole given by subjects to tribal leaders, for the sake of better status and benefits. In Greece, there was a system of *ephoria* – civil servants with judicial and executive powers, which was the most important source of corruption, as 'a crime committed not for the sake of obtaining the necessary, but for obtaining the superfluous' (Aristotle, 1960: 1270). In Rome, Caesar went to war in Gaul to fight against the barbarians, but also to secure income for the state and military service. The Ottoman Empire had a similar form of reward as the sultans allowed judges to receive gifts when applying Sharia law (Aras, 2007: 25-27).

In the Middle Ages, corruption was also present and this phenomenon was criticized by philosophers from the time of humanism and the Renaissance, as well as English philosophers, such as Dante, Machiavelli, Montesquieu, More, Bacon and others. Humanists and philosophers in the US also had a critical approach to corruption, which they believed to be a product of the system, but also influenced by human nature regardless of the geographic component. The society of that time was accustomed to corruption, and

the prevailing attitude was that it was justified to buy public positions, to choose civil servants according to their origin and financial status (Teofilović, 2007: 11-15).

In the new century, especially after the end of World War II, the earlier doctrines and protection system (England), spoils system (USA) and electoral nepotism (France) were abandoned. A new system of professional administration, selection and training of personnel, impartial execution of work, respect for laws and professional standards is advocated (Aras, 2007: 25-27).

4. INTERNATIONAL LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK FOR COMBATING CORRUPTION

The international legal framework for combating corruption includes several specialized documents, the most important of which are: UN Convention against Corruption, 2004 (UNCAC), Criminal Law Convention on Corruption, European Treaty Series - No. 173, 1999 (Criminal LCC), Civil Law Convention on Corruption, European Treaty Series – No. 174, 1999 (Civil LCC) and UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, 2001, (UNCATOC). The aforementioned conventions were adopted by the Republic of Serbia, i.e. the predecessor states, and solutions from these documents were incorporated into the legal order of Serbia.

The UNCAC imposed the obligation of the signatory states to adopt preventive anti-corruption policy measures and positive practices related to the development, implementation and maintenance of the same policy in their national legislation. Furthermore, it is envisaged to review legal instruments and issued measures with the aim of preventing corrupt actions, establishing preventive independent bodies and hiring specialized personnel for the implementation of anti-corruption activities.

The UNCAC imposes the obligation of the signatory states to criminalize in their national criminal legislation corrupt criminal acts related to: bribery of domestic civil servants, bribery of foreign civil servants and representatives of international organizations; embezzlement; illegal appropriation or similar diversion of property by a civil servant; influence peddling; abuse of official position; illegal enrichment; bribery in the private sector, embezzlement of property in the private sector and laundering of proceeds (money) obtained from a criminal act. In accordance with the above, it is also the obligation of the signatory states to criminalize in national legislation the responsibility of legal entities for the aforementioned actions, then to issue the punishment of accomplices, aides and instigators in committing and attempting to commit these criminal acts, as well as all actions undertaken with the aim of obstructing justice.

The Criminal LCC imposes the obligation of the signatory states to criminalize (corruption) criminal acts related to: active and passive bribery of domestic civil servants in their national criminal legislation; bribery of members of domestic and foreign state authorities, bodies and officials; active and passive bribery in the private sector; bribery of officials of international organizations and members of international parliamentary bodies; bribery of judges and officials of international courts; influence peddling; money laundering, acquired through offences related to corruption and criminalization of accounting criminal acts.

The Civil LCC Imposes the obligation of the signatory states to provide compensation for damages in their national legislation, provided that the defendant committed or approved an act of corruption or failed to take reasonable steps to prevent it from happening, with the existence of damage on the part of the plaintiff and the existence of a causal link between the commission of corruption and the resulting damage.

According to Article 2 of the Civil LCC, corruption is defined as any act that includes asking, offering, giving or receiving a bribe, directly or indirectly, or any other illegal act of obtaining benefits. These are actions that violate the legal and proper performance of duties or that demand illegal behavior from the recipient of the bribe, as well as the acquisition of illegal benefits. It is very important to emphasize that the Civil LCC formed a specialized Group of Council of Europe against corruption called GRECO (<https://www.coe.int/en/web/greco>). The GRECO is in charge of monitoring the implementation of the Civil LCC in the fight against corruption and in this capacity monitors the member states, which visits and prepares evaluation reports on the existence and representation of corruption in each specific country, with a proposal of recommendations for the most successful fight against corruption.

UNCATOC or colloquially ‘The Palermo Convention’, among other things, establishes the obligation of the signatory states to criminalize corrupt criminal acts in their national legislation and to adopt measures to fight corruption. Additional protocols to the Convention are: Protocol for prevention, suppression and punishment of trafficking in human beings, especially women and children, Protocol against smuggling of migrants by land, sea and air and Protocol against illegal production and trafficking of firearms, their parts, assemblies and ammunition (Nikač, 2015: 265-290).

According to the provisions of the Palermo Convention (Articles 8-10), corruption is defined as any promise, offer or giving of an inappropriate benefit to a civil servant, in order to act or refrain from acting in the performance of his official duties, but also any request or acceptance of an inappropriate benefit by a civil servant in order to act or refrain from acting in the performance of official duties. The category of civil servants is broadly defined as all persons who work in public services, which was also accepted by the legislator in Serbia (According to Article 2 of the Civil Servant Law, the Official Gazette of the RS, Nos. 79/05, 81/05)

The obligation of the signatory states to adopt anti-corruption measures and determine the effective action of state authorities in order to prevent, detect and punish corrupt civil servants is foreseen. Accordingly, it is necessary to ensure the independence of professional bodies in order to prevent inappropriate influences on their work. The Palermo Convention is a revolutionary document for the fight against organized crime and provides for the formation of special bodies for the fight against organized crime (court, prosecutor's office, police, prison), then the use of special investigative techniques and measures, the harmonization of the norms of national legislation with the Palermo Convention, etc.

5. NATIONAL LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK OF SERBIA FOR COMBATING CORRUPTION

The legislative framework of the Republic of Serbia was amended during 2016, when the current Criminal Code (Official Gazette of the RS, Nos. 85/05, 88/05 – Corrigendum, 107/05 – Corrigendum, 72/09, 111/09, 121/12, 104/13, 108/14, 94/16, 35/19 and 94/24 <https://propisi.pravno-informacioni-sistem.rs/content/126>) was amended, as well as the adoption of the new Law on the Organization and Competence of State Authorities in Suppression of Organized Crime, Terrorism and Corruption (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 94/16 and 10/23 <https://propisi.pravno-informacioni-sistem.rs/content/1610>). In addition to new normative solutions, a new organization of authorities that should participate in the suppression of corrupt criminal acts was also adopted.

The Criminal Code was amended at the end of 2016, when a new composition of felonies against the economy was implemented. The amendments entered into force the following year (June 1st 2017), while one part of the provisions began to be applied later (March 1st 2018). The same amendments to the Criminal Code incriminate more (7) new felonies against the economy, but they are not specifically listed in the section-head under the heading of corrupt felonies. In the period 2002 – 2005, there was a special chapter of Criminal Code called Corruption crimes, which included the following crimes: Corruption in administrative bodies, Misappropriation of funds from the budget, Corruption in public procurement, Corruption in the privatization process, Corruption in the judiciary, Abuse of the function of a defence attorney or attorney, Corruption in health, Corruption in education, and Fixing the outcome of competitions. At the time, the systematics of these felonies were carried out mainly according to the areas where corruption appeared, and a particular problem was the fact that the concept of corruption was not uniquely defined in the text of the law. Therefore, different interpretations were applied in the practice of the authorities, primarily a broader (extensive) and narrower (restrictive) interpretation of which acts belong to the area of corrupt felonies.

According to the current rulings of the Criminal Code, corrupt felonies are considered to be those that mainly relate to the areas (protected object) of the economy and official duties, as well as certain acts from other areas. Within Chapter XXII, felonies against the economy are issued, including corrupt felonies: Tax Avoidance, Abuse of Position of a Responsible Person, Abuse Concerning Public Procurement, Abuse in Privatization Procedure, Accepting Bribes in Conducting of Business Activity, Giving Bribe in Conducting of Business Activity, Causing Bankruptcy, Causing False Bankruptcy, and Money Laundering. Within the framework of Chapter XXXIII, felonies against official duty and among them corrupt felonies are provided: Abuse of Office, Violation of Law by a Judge, Public Prosecutor or his Deputy, Dereliction of Duty, Unlawful Collection and Payment, Improper Use of Budget Funds, Fraud in Service, Embezzlement, Unauthorized Use, Influence Peddling, Soliciting and Accepting Bribes, and Bribery. In other chapters of the CC, there are also certain felonies that are corrupt, such as: within the felonies against electoral rights – Giving and Accepting Bribes in connection with Voting, within the felonies against labor rights – Violation of the Right to Employment and during Unemployment.

Law on the Organization and Competence of State Authorities in Suppression of Organized Crime, Terrorism and Corruption (OCGL) determines which felonies it refers to in terms of corruption, thus adopting mostly identical solutions as stated above. In addition, this is the so-called ‘organizational law’ that issues the organization of public authorities such as the courts, the prosecution and the police in the fight against corruption.

Other laws of importance for combating corruption are also important and among them the following stand out: Criminal Procedure Code (Official Gazette of the RS, Nos. 72/11, 101/11, 121/12, 32/13, 45/13, 55/14, 35/19 and 27/21-CC), Law on Confiscation of Property Derived from Criminal Activity (Official Gazette of the RS, Nos. 32/13, 94/16 and 35/19), Law on the Protection Programme for Participants in Criminal Proceedings (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 85/05), Law on the Anti-Corruption Agency (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 97/08, 53/10, 66/11 – CC, 67/13 – CC, 112/13 – authentic interpretation, 08/15 – CC and 88/19), Law on Whistleblowers' Protection (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 128/14) etc. Corruption is normatively defined in the Law on the Anti-Corruption Agency as ‘a relationship based on abuse of an official, i.e. social position or influence, in the public or private sector, with the aim of obtaining personal benefit or

benefit for another'. The Law on Confiscation of Property Derived from Criminal Activity issues opportunities for the confiscation of property benefits achieved through corrupt actions through the financial investigation process conducted by the police and the prosecutor's office. Law on the Protection Programme for Participants in Criminal Proceedings issues opportunities for the smooth conduct of the proceedings and the protection of all actors whose safety is at risk.

In addition to the legal framework, an important legal source is various regulations, among which the National Strategy for the Fight against Corruption for the period 2024-2028 (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 63/24), action plans and other documents stand out.

6. INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS OF THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

OCGL establishes new institutional mechanisms in the fight against corruption in the Republic of Serbia. Chapter III of the same regulation issues the organization and competence of state bodies in the fight against corruption (art. 13-18). Special bodies in the form of departments are foreseen at the level of the public prosecutor, the court and the police. According to Article 13, special departments of the Higher Public Prosecutor Office for combating corruption are foreseen, then a special police unit within the MoI of the RS and special departments of higher courts for combating corruption.

Special Anti-Corruption Departments of the High Court act in the first instance in relation to corrupt criminal acts prosecuted by the prosecution. These special departments exist in Belgrade, Kraljevo, Niš and Novi Sad. The work of the department is managed by the president of the special department, who is appointed by the president of the Higher Court (mandate of 4 years). The staffing of judges is done by the president of the Higher Court, who assigns the judges of the Higher Court, for a period of 6 years and with written consent. Also, in case of need, the High Council of the Judiciary can send a judge from another court to work in a special anti-corruption department, for a period of 6 years and with written consent. The president of the Higher Court regulates the work of the special anti-corruption department.

The Serbian public prosecutor acts in cases of corrupt felonies through Higher Public Prosecutor's Offices located in Belgrade, Kraljevo, Niš and Novi Sad, where special anti-corruption departments are formed. The work of each special anti-corruption department is managed by an appointed manager, who is appointed by the competent chief prosecutor. Acting prosecutors are assigned or referred to these departments from among former deputy prosecutors, now public prosecutors. Staffing is guided by the reasons for the needs of the service and the selection of candidates who have the necessary knowledge, skills and experience in combating crimes in the field of economic crime, acts against official duty and corruption. When appointing or referring to work in a special department for the fight against corruption, the consent of the deputy public prosecutor is necessary in case he is appointed or referred from a public prosecutor's office in which a special anti-corruption department has not been established.

The police have their own Special Anti-Corruption Department, which is part of the Criminal Police Directorate, but which is relatively independent in its work and related to cooperation with the Special Anti-Corruption Department of the Prosecutor's Office. At the headquarters of the criminal police in Belgrade, there is the Anti-Corruption Department, which coordinates work for the territory of entire Serbia, while at the level of the cities there are Sections (a total of 8) in the form of detachments, namely: Subotica,

Novi Sad, Belgrade, Kragujevac, Zaječar, Niš, Kraljevo and Užice (<https://informator.poverenik.rs>).

The work methodology (or Standard Operating Procedures) of these organizational units is the same as for other units within the criminal police, but specially adapted to the sensitive area they cover. The anti-corruption department and sections have close cooperation with the prosecution, especially because they act according to the direct orders of the prosecutor and in accordance with the law. For the sake of better cooperation, a coordinator for cooperation between the police and the prosecutor's office has been appointed within each department. Issues such as deadlines, procedures and official communication between the prosecutor's office and the police in the field of combating corruption are regulated by a joint legal act of the Minister of Justice and the Minister of the Interior. In addition, the Minister of the Interior issues a special act that more closely regulates the organization and policing of the special anti-corruption unit. Within the Combating Organized Crime Service, there is a special Department for High Corruption in cases involving elements of felonies of corruption in the context of organized crime, which is all under the jurisdiction of the Prosecutor's Office for Organized Crime (Further reading: Leštanin, Nikač 2016).

Specialized bodies for assistance and support to special anti-corruption departments of the prosecution are also issued by OCGL. Thus, the possibility of establishing a Financial Forensics Service is foreseen, within which expert work is performed by experts, as a rule, in the economic profession, who help prosecutors in the analysis of money flows and financial transactions. The law issues that financial forensic experts are experts who possess adequate knowledge in the field of finance, accounting, auditing, banking, stock exchange and business operations. The law also issues the mutual cooperation of all state authorities through liaison officers in order to achieve cooperation and provide data, with the aim of more efficient criminal prosecution for corrupt crimes. The next type of cooperation in the fight against corruption consists of strike groups, which represent a mechanism of cooperation, coordination and joint work formed by the decision of the competent prosecutor with the consent of the Supreme Public Prosecutor, with the aim of detecting and prosecuting crimes that are the subject of the work of the strike group. Other important elements of importance for the normal work and functioning of specialized bodies for the fight against corruption are the training of personnel, data on property status (property card), security checks and keeping data confidential.

7. RESULTS

Semantically, the word corruption originates from the Latin term *corruptio*, which in translation means corruption, depravity, debauchery; bribing, bribery; decay, decomposition; forgery (Vujaklija, 1980: 472). The definition of corruption is not uniquely determined in doctrine and practice because different – sociological, legal, mixed, etc. (Nikač, 2015: 32-38). Sociological definitions start from the broader social perception of corruption and undefined general good and public interest, while legal definitions start from corruption as a criminal act and specific criminal offences. In the author's opinion, the most expedient is a mixed (legal-sociological) determination that equally respects the social environment and the norms of positive law (Further readings in Milutinović, 1990: 34).

In modern society, primacy is given by functional definitions given by reference institutions, such as the World Bank, which considers corruption to be the abuse of a public position for the purpose of private gain (Teofilović, 2007: 23). A similar position is

taken by Transparency International, which under corruption means abuse of power for private gain (Further readings in Nikač, 2009: 408-424).

The most important elements of corruption are public authority (original or derived), abuse of authority and obtaining illegal (property) benefit for oneself or another (Poup, Skopjak, Nikolić, Nenadić, 2004: 3). The most important forms and types of corruption are: individual, systemic, indirect, competition, active and passive, and other forms – institutional and idiosyncratic; conventional and indirect; street, contractual and political; transactional, extortion and investment; nepotistic and autogenously (Derenčinović, 2000: 130-134).

The authors believe that the presented international documents are a good basis for establishing a joint fight against organized crime, corruption and other most serious forms of crime, as well as for establishing better international cooperation between states and international organizations. On the national level, these documents were important for the harmonization of norms and the adoption of good legal solutions, as well as for a more effective multi-agency approach of state authorities and bodies in the fight against organized crime and suppression of corruption.

The national legislation of Serbia in the field of combating corruption consists of several codes or laws that regulate criminal liability and the organization of public authorities. This legislation regulates the institutional mechanisms of each public authority in the fight against corruption. The system established in this way is in line with the most important international resolutions. In the practice of work of public authorities, cooperation on the internal level is very important, which takes place on a multi-sector, i.e. multi-agency level, while international cooperation with other countries and international organizations takes place on the external level. Multi-agency cooperation in the field of internal affairs, security and crime prevention takes place through the National Security Council, which is headed by the President of the Republic. The Council is significantly assisted in its work by the Bureau for Coordination, which operationally coordinates the work of the security services and executes the Council's conclusions on issues within its jurisdiction. In the work of these bodies, the relevant ministers (army, police, justice, etc.) and representatives of the police, intelligence agencies, military security services, the Supreme Court and the Supreme Public Prosecutor's Office and others, depending on the subject of consideration, participate in the work of these bodies as permanent members or by invitation. Representatives of these and other authorities exchange information and coordinate joint activities, potentially in the area of combating corruption in the community.

8. CONCLUSION

In addition to terrorism and organized crime, one of the most serious forms of criminality is certainly corruption, especially since it has gained the right of citizenship in numerous communities and has become a system of life. Today, corruption is a problem in a large number of countries in the world, especially less developed and countries in transition. This phenomenon seriously threatens to collapse the previous achievements of the developed world and human civilization, because the regular work and life of people in the community becomes meaningless. It also threatens to shake the foundations of a democratic society and undermine the work of all state bodies and citizens' trust in the state, its bodies and their work.

Corruption is significantly present in countries in transition, such as the countries of the former socialist bloc and ex SFRY, where it has successfully adapted to social, political and economic changes. In these countries, it took on some new forms and even more dangerous forms, because the transition environment significantly contributed to the development of corruption at all levels of society. Some of the ex-socialist countries managed to overcome the difficult time of transition, harmonize legislation with EU law and build institutional mechanisms to combat corruption. The best example is the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary and Romania, which are equal EU member states today. The former YU republics of Slovenia and Croatia, which today are also equal members of the EU, had the same experience. Other member states of the former SFRY are currently in the process of transition and joining the EU, as is the case with North Macedonia, Montenegro and Bosnia and Herzegovina. The mentioned countries have also encountered organized crime, terrorism, and other most serious forms of crime and, of course, corruption.

Serbia is also an applicant country for admission to the EU, but with a lot of delays in the last 10-15 years, when the process of reforms in society seems to have stopped and admission to the EU is uncertain. Serbia has opened a lot of chapters or so-called clusters (groups of chapters) in different areas, among which Chapter no. 23 and 24 relating to defence and security, justice and internal affairs. The authors believe that Serbia has good legislative solutions based on verified international documents, but that in practice the desired results have not been achieved because the community is probably not yet ready for radical cuts. The situation is the same in the fight against crime and its most dangerous forms, especially against corruption. The formation of new organizational forms of the police, prosecutor's office and court in the form of specialized bodies for combating corruption is particularly important. These bodies have achieved good initial results, but it seems that there is a lack of greater support from the community and political structures.

A successful fight against corruption requires, first of all, a change of consciousness among citizens, then a change in the environment in society and the education of citizens in which the devastating consequences of corruption in the community would be constantly pointed out. Perhaps there is room for thinking to make some *de lege ferenda* changes in the existing framework, especially to adapt to the new ambient conditions and emerging forms of corruption in the public (state) sector. At the end, authors add that transparency in the work of all authorities is a necessary prerequisite for the successful suppression of corruption, while respecting the rules of criminal procedure and the secrecy of certain stages of the procedure.

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